

Root-knot disease of rice in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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Local and improved rice varieties have been found infested with root-knot nematodes in the Mekong Delta. The summer and winter crops using improved varieties were more seriously attacked than the main crop. Despite galls in the root systems, the main crop was seldom damaged, because it had

standing water in the field. Floating rice varieties such as Nang-Tay also were infested. The nematode on Nang-Tay was identified by C. Germani as *Meloidogyne graminicola*.

Two studies of damage to height and yield of rice variety TN 73-2 and methods of control were done in the field in Kien-Giang Province. At 30 days after sowing, gall numbers averaged 13-15/plant. The nematode decreased plant height by about 3 148% and rice yield by about 65%.

Either continuous flooding or application of carbofuran and diazinon in irri-

gation water was highly effective control, increasing yield 100-160% over that in the untreated plots and 70-90% over that in the nondiseased plots. Both chemicals gave good control at 10 and 20 kg commercial product/ha to 20 days after treatment. Then, gall numbers began to increase but did not cause damage. Continuous flooding gave slower results, but the longer the flooding, the fewer the number of galls. Flooding the field with tidewater was not effective. Neither control method had much effect at booting. ■

Field soil as a source of rice stem nematodes

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The Baermann-funnel extraction method was used to determine the pres-

ence of rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* in submerged field soil in the infested rice-producing region of An-Giang and Hau-Giang Provinces. Infested soil contained 8-12 living nematodes in 90 ml of soil at the 0-20 cm depth and 3-7 nematodes at 204 cm depth.

D. angustus was not observed in soil

samples dried for 1.5 months. Dried infested soil was used to grow rice plants in the greenhouse. Disease symptoms were recorded 2 months after transplanting. Infested seedlings were 14.2% to 18.1% in dry soil from the 0-20 cm depth and 12.1% to 14.4% in dry soil from the 20-40 cm depth. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Parasites of the rice slug caterpillar

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A slug caterpillar, *Latoia (Parasa) bicolor* Walker (Lepidoptera: Limacodidae), regularly appears on rice in Coochbehar, Jalpaiguri, and in the plains of Darjeeling near the foothills of the sub-Himalayan ranges. The spined caterpillars cause extensive foliar damage from July to October, often necessitating retransplanting. Grubs cause severe dermal itching and urticaria on touch.

The arthropod enemies of *L. bicolor* are two hymenopterous parasitoids: *Brachymeria euploae* Westwood (Chalcidoidea: Chalcididae) and *Goryphus busilaris* Holmgren [Ichneumonidea: Ichneumonidae]. They parasitize 24% of the pest's pupae in the field. In general, third and fourth generations of *L. bicolor* are more parasitized. ■

Sepedon spegeus (Fabr.) (Sciomyzidae) and *Notiphila* spp. (Ephydriidae): alternate hosts of *Trichogramma japonicum* Ashmead, a rice stem borer egg parasite

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In the Philippines, *Trichogramma japonicum* Ashmead is a common egg parasite of rice stem borers *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Chilo suppressalis*, and *C. polychrysus*. Eggs of two genera of flies that inhabit rice fields — *Sepedon spegeus* (Fabr.) (Sciomyzidae) and *Notiphila latigenis* Hendel, *N. similis* Meijere and *N. spinosa* Cresson (Ephydriidae) — were collected in the field in

Incidence of parasitization by *Trichogramma japonicum* on eggs of *Sepedon spegeus* and *Notiphila* spp. collected from 6 fields in the Philippines, 1981-82.

Province	Municipality	Sampling date	<i>Sepedon spegeus</i>		<i>Notiphila</i> spp. ^a	
			Eggs held (no.)	Parasitization (%)	Eggs held (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Cagayan	Solana	23 Sep 1981	6	0	14	14.3
	Laguna	23-27 Nov 1981	11	36.4	52	8.0
Agusan del Sur	Del Monte	7-17 Dec 1981	5	20.0	181	2.0
		18-29 Jan 1982	18	5.5	162	7.4
		8-24 Feb 1982	24	8.3	234	10.3
		26 Jul 1981	0	—	24	0
Bukidnon	Kalilangan	29 Jul 1981	0	—	36	6.0
North Cotabato	Kabacan	4-6 Jan 1982	0	—	22	5.0
Zamboanga del Sur	Pagadian	3-4 Aug 1981	6	0	18	—

^a*Notiphila latigenis* Hendel, *N. similis* Meijere, and *N. spinosa* Cresson.